

**SM5. Frost shocks negatively impact the supply of
high-stem juicing apples in Switzerland –
Supplementary materials**

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Figure S1.1. Two-way fixed effects regression model showing the estimated effect of frost exposure on apple supply, controlling for both unit (PLZ postcode) and time (year) fixed effects. The dashed line at $x = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ delineates the knot separating the two temperature intervals. The shaded area represents 95% confidence bands when errors are clustered by year and PLZ postcode.

Figure S1.2. Individual fixed effects regression model showing the estimated effect of frost exposure on the quantity of apples collected. The dashed line at $x = -2^{\circ}\text{C}$ delineates the knot separating the two temperature intervals. The shaded area represents 95% confidence bands when errors are clustered by year and PLZ postcode.

Figure S1.3. Individual fixed effects regression model showing the estimated effect of frost exposure on the quantity of apples collected. The dashed line at $x = -1^{\circ}\text{C}$ delineates the knot separating the two temperature intervals. The shaded area represents 95% confidence bands when errors are clustered by year and PLZ postcode.

Figure S1.4. Individual fixed effects regression model showing the estimated two-period latent effect of past frost exposure on the quantity of apples collected, accounting for biennial bearing. The dashed line at $x = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ delineates the knot separating the two temperature intervals. The shaded area represents 95% confidence bands when errors are clustered by year and PLZ postcode.

Figure S1.5. Individual fixed effects regression model showing the estimated one-period latent effect of frost exposure on the quantity of apples collected. The dashed line at $x = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ delineates the knot separating the two temperature intervals. The shaded area represents 95% confidence bands when errors are clustered by year and PLZ postcode.

Figure S1.6. Individual fixed effects regression model showing the estimated effect of frost exposure on apple supply, subsampling for postcodes west (in blue) and east (in red) of the median longitude, controlling for both unit (PLZ postcode) and time (year) fixed effects. The dashed line at $x = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ delineates the knot separating the two temperature intervals. The shaded area represents 95% confidence bands when errors are clustered by year and PLZ postcode.

Figure S1.7. Individual fixed effects regression model showing the estimated effect of frost exposure on apple supply, subsampling for postcodes north (in blue) and south (in red) of the median latitude, controlling for both unit (PLZ postcode) and time (year) fixed effects. The dashed line at $x = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ delineates the knot separating the two temperature intervals. The shaded area represents 95% confidence bands when errors are clustered by year and PLZ postcode.

Figure S1.8. Type-1 Tobit regression model showing the estimated effect of frost exposure on apple supply, controlling for unit (PLZ postcode) fixed effects. The dashed line at $x = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ delineates the knot separating the two temperature intervals. No confidence bands are shown since the estimated errors are biased.